

Interpolating Contours to Raster-Based DEM With Further Hillshading

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1 What This All Is About

As I was working for a project in Venezuela to integrate external geographic datasets into our Geographic Information System (GIS) I had to interpolate a raster-based Digital Elevation Model (DEM) (figure 1) from contour lines which I received from an official department. There are many different approaches which can be basically divided in OpenSource and commercial ones. I compared the results of two functions in GRASS GIS 6.4 [1] and a corresponding function in ArcGIS 9.3 [2] and came to the conclusion that the results achieved by ArcGIS are better for my purposes. The goal of all this work was to get a detailed hillshade [3] also suitable for large scale mapping applications. Digital elevation data can come along in different formats:

- As raw ASCII¹ file containing a matrix of elevation values,
- as raster image (figure 1) with up to 32 bit for one grey-channel,
- as vector dataset containing points with elevation information,
- as a vector or raster dataset containing contour lines which represent different levels of elevation,
- as derivation of these possibilities.

Usually high resolution Digital Elevation Models in raster format for big areas of interest require high amount of physical storage space. In Venezuela the official departments provide detailed contour line datasets in vector format to reduce the storage space for data exchange.

If it is desired to represent geographic relief information in two-dimensional mapping applications, a shaded relief, also called hillshade, can accomplish this task very well. It emphasizes terrain characteristics depicting realistic shadow distribution of sunlight. To be able to create such a hillshade out of vector-based contour lines, a raster-based DEM has to be interpolated in advance because the common hillshading algorithms require raster data to process the shading. There are many different approaches to create a shaded relief, just applying one hillshade algorithm may be enough in some cases, in others post-processing is necessary. Usually shaded reliefs for large scale mapping look different than

¹ American Standard Code for Information Interchange

for small scale mapping. For large scale mapping often visualisation of general landforms is sufficient whereas small scale applications can profit from details visible in the terrain. My area of interest covers the whole “El Avila” national park and the state “Vargas” at Venezuela’s central coast line. Geographic data about this area is going to be presented in a WebGIS and in future other students will extend the GIS with survey data of different disciplines like geography, biology and tourism. The terrain model together with additional environmental data will deal as context for the survey data.

485	484	482	480	477	474	469	465	460	456	451	446	441
485	483	481	479	476	472	468	463	458	453	448	444	439
485	483	481	478	474	470	465	461	456	451	446	441	436
484	482	479	476	472	468	463	458	453	448	443	438	434
483	481	478	474	470	466	461	456	451	446	441	436	431
482	480	476	472	468	463	458	453	448	443	438	433	428
481	478	474	470	465	461	455	450	445	440	435	430	426
480	476	472	468	463	458	453	448	442	437	432	428	423
478	474	470	465	460	455	450	445	440	434	430	425	421

Fig. 1: Example of raster cells containing hight information in metres. Decreasing elevation to the bottom-left corner.

2 Interpolating the Raster-DEM

To create a hillshade, first a raster-based Digital Elevation Model is necessary. A covering raster can be interpolated from contour lines or point data for example. Interpolating contour lines to a raster-based DEM has the disadvantage that peak elevations like mountain peaks can only hardly be included in the result. ArcGIS offers the possibility to interpolate different datasets in the same process, one containing contour lines and one containing points for peak elevations for example. In my case this issue is unimportant because I only had access to the contour dataset. The following three sections describe different approaches which I tested to interpolate a raster-DEM from contour lines. The figures on page 4 and 5 summarise my results.

2.1 GRASS GIS: `r.surf.contour`-Function

GRASS GIS as one of the most popular OpenSource GIS offers a great catalogue of tools to manipulate vector and raster data. One of two functions to interpolate contour lines to a raster-based DEM is the `r.surf.contour`-function which in general produces pretty usable results. This function is quite outdated so for example it can not create floating-point outputs which is the biggest disadvantage. At the first glance this seems not to be crucial because depending of the horizontal resolution, integer values representing the height should provide enough accuracy. But if you want to create a hillshade out of this integer-DEM, you will get problems with terracing effects in flat areas unless smoothing the DEM in advance with a filter, see section 3. The smoothing results in loss of detail but can eliminate the terracing effect, so you have to decide if this possibility is appropriate for your purposes. This function works only with contour lines in raster format and treats cells with the value of 0 as `NODATA` which for example means that if your contours contain a coast line represented by the value 0, this part is not being included in the interpolation process. You can avoid that by adding the value 1 to all raster cells of the input and subtracting 1 after the interpolation process from the output. But once you got so far you have to deal with long running times of this algorithm. A flood filling algorithm [4] is used which shows low performance the bigger the distance between each contour line is, the running time increases exponentially. Processing the area of approximately 70 km² took around two hours. The final DEM is slightly coarse and shows vertical rims in steep regions, see figure 2.

2.2 GRASS GIS: `v.surf.rst`-Function

The `v.surf.rst`-function of GRASS GIS is an alternative and accepts contour lines in vector format to perform different topographic operations using a regularized spline with tension [5] [6] interpolation method. The output is written in floating-point values which comes in handy for later hillshading. Using it only for raster surface creation, the interpolation of the 70 km² area took around one hour with a generally cleaner result compared to `r.surf.contour`-function. There are no vertical rims left, in general the surface is smoother but emphasizes steep parts with more detail at the same time. The algorithm shows problems in flat areas, applying a hillshade you have to deal with block effects, see figure 3. Smoothing the DEM even several times before hillshading does not satisfyingly correct this problem.

2.3 ArcGIS: Topo to Raster-Function

Besides of OpenSource products there are many different commercial software solutions. One of these I worked with is ArcGIS from ESRI [2]. The `Topo to Raster`-function included in ArcGIS 9.3 is an algorithm from ANUDEM [7], bought in from Australia. It took a while to be able to work with the `Topo to Raster`-function because every time trying to interpolate my contour lines to a raster I

Fig. 2: Result of GRASS GIS' `r.surf.contour`-function with hillshade after applying a 3x3 `mean`-filter. Still some terracing effect visible in flat areas due to dealing with integer values for hillshading. Steep areas show some kind of vertical rims.

Fig. 3: Result of GRASS GIS' `v.surf.rst`-function with hillshade. Block effect visible in flat areas.

Fig. 4: Result of ArcGIS' **Topo to Raster**-function with hillshade applied on the raw floating-point DEM without any smoothing or post-processing. Flat areas are interpolated without encountering any terracing or block effects in the later applied hillshade.

got new error messages about not having enough system memory or the contour layer containing too many points for the chosen output resolution of the raster. The contour lines are quite detailed and have a stepping of 20 m, I wanted to interpolate a raster with 5 m horizontal resolution. After studying the ArcGIS Help and consulting Google [8], I decided to divide my area of interest which covers around 4400 km² into 16 smaller parts, each covering 275 km². Now I was able to interpolate the raster for each of these 16 masks without encountering any error messages, seems that the whole dataset was just too much for the algorithm. Nice, the resulting 16 DEMs have been combined with the **Mosaic**-function to one grand dataset again. Taking a look at figure 4, the result is nice and my Python script [9] which automatically interpolates all 16 parts took only about 1 hour, great improvement comparing to the **r.surf.contour**-function of GRASS GIS which would have taken nearly five days for the whole area of 4400 km².

The result had to be evaluated. All in all the single interpolations look great but there arise problems regarding the borders of each of the 16 parts. In flat areas like a city basin for example, the algorithm does not correctly interpolate the border lines of the output raster, see figure 5. This happens because in flat areas the distance between contour lines can reach up to some kilometres and when unfortunately this area is split up to perform partial interpolations like in my case, the interpolation algorithm has problems including distant contour

lines for the calculation of each border line. Later on when merging all single adjacent rasters to one part using the `Mosaic`-function you see hard break-lines in these flat areas, no parameter configuration of the `Mosaic`-function could improve this issue significantly. The `Topo to Raster`-algorithm offers a parameter called “margin” to reduce this effect but trying around with different values for this parameters did not lead to a perfect result, every time there were break-lines in the same places. The value for “margin” tells the algorithm how many cells beyond the output’s boundary to include for interpolation of the boundary edge. Even with a value of 2000, which correspond 10 km with my cell size of 5 m, break-lines were still existent. Two whole days of testing of different approaches to obtain a mosaic without partial break-lines did not result in success. In the end I evaluated all borders of the 16 single parts manually and inserted additional masks into the interpolation process, covering erroneous areas. As a result I got 31 masks of different sizes distributed over my area of 4400 km², see figure 6. The interpolation including the hillshade generation took just one and a half hour as automated process. No break-lines left but plenty of working time lost to find a satisfying solution, regarding the final product it was worth it.

Fig. 5: Result of ArcGIS’ `Topo to Raster`-function with hillshade. In this case hillshading has been applied on an integer version of the raster to emphasize the break-lines. Terracing effect when dealing with integer DEMs is clearly visible. The break-lines occur at the borders of the individually interpolated parts in flat areas where the distance between contour lines is big. Unfortunately the region of Caracas has been divided into four parts.

Fig. 6: Overview of the 16 major masks and 15 minor to correct erroneous areas. The DEM was interpolated for each of these bounding boxes with `Topo to Raster`-function, then all partial results were combined using `Mosaic`-function of ArcGIS with the “BLEND”-Parameter.

3 Hillshading

The goal was to achieve a detailed hillshade of the area of interest. My earlier DEM extracted from stereographic ASTER² data only had a horizontal resolution of 30 m, the created hillshade was not satisfying for large scale mapping applications like a WebGIS with regional data just covering small areas of short hiking paths for example, see figure 7. As already mentioned in section 2.1, the hillshading algorithms³ have problems with integer input rasters due to the harder stepping of integer values, compare figures 2 and 5. In this case the resultant hillshade shows terracing effects, above all in flat areas. Working with floating-point data eliminates these effects nearly completely. If only integer datasets are at hand, a rectangle filter of 3x3 or 5x5 cells with a `Mean`-function applied on the DEM before hillshading reduces these effects as well, but leads to loss of details and blurs the DEM noticeably. To eliminate all terraces you have to apply the filter one to three times, losing more and more detail every loop.

Experimenting with the `Hillshade`-function of ArcGIS and GRASS GIS I got best results with a sun azimuth of 315° (from north-east) and its elevation of 65°. Using a lower sun elevation (45° for example) emphasizes major landforms due to stronger contrast between shadows and sun-exposed areas, but also leads so less details visible in the sun-exposed slopes because these become very light, see figure 8(a). On the other hand, using a high sun elevation (75° for example) reveals more details in the sun-exposed regions as well as in the shadowed regions but makes it difficult to recognise major landforms, see figure 8(b). An elevation of 65° offers a good compromise for my purpose but it always depends on the characteristics of the terrain you are working with.

My 65°-result has been combined with a slope-depicting version which is achieved when using a light source directly from above, just performing the `Hillshade`-function with a light source elevation of 90°. Zones with small slope

² Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer [10]

³ Of GRASS GIS and ArcGIS

Fig. 7: Hillshade of a DEM with 30 m horizontal resolution extracted from stereographic ASTER [10] imagery data. For mapping applications of this scale it may not reveal enough details.

Fig. 8: Hillshade with sun elevation of 45° emphasizes major landforms (a), whereas hillshade with sun elevation of 75° reveals more terrain details (b).

are represented in light and zones with high slope in dark colours. Combining both results in Adobe Photoshop [11] or GIMP [12] gives stronger appearance to mountain ridges. For my small scale hillshade I additionally used an aerial perspective effect which also is known as the “Swiss Style” [13] because supposedly Swiss cartographers originally used it for their maps. This effect blurs/softens areas with low altitude and gives more contrast to zones with high altitude like mountain peaks.

Working with geographically referenced rasters in image processing software like Photoshop or GIMP can be a problem because you will lose the core information: your geographic reference. ArcGIS offers a tool to export a textual reference description⁴ of your raster which you can easily use later on to re-reference your final image. All in all it took a few days to experiment with these different possibilities visualising my terrain of interest because there exists no thumb rule how to do it perfectly, it is always a question of data quality, terrain characteristics and the application you want to use the result for.

4 Further Encountered Problems

First of all the contour dataset had an error in its projected coordinates. It already came along referenced in the desired geographic coordinate reference system REGVEN [14] with a projection in UTM Zone 19N [15] but showed an offset of around 50 m to north-east. This offset was corrected using a two-dimensional translation function with manually chosen control points. During the following evaluation of the DEM’s interpolation result there arose further errors, some of them could be corrected, others not. Obviously the contour dataset contained digitalization errors, so some features had wrong elevation information stored, see figure 9. The parts printed in white emphasize the wrong attribute data. In the western part, following a contour of 2340 m you see a contour of 2260 m which is rather unrealistic, it should be 2360 m. In the eastern part the contour of 2220 m is split up, the adjacent to the east has an elevation of 2120 m, which obviously seems to be an error as well. The hillshade of the DEM shows these errors as dramatic cuts in landscape.

Comparing figure 10 you see that the contour dataset includes data from different datasets, the hard rectangle-shaped cut is due to merging a contour dataset of poor quality to the parent one which is more detailed. These two datasets have not been connected correctly. The north-western part shows the detailed parent dataset, to the south-east you see a change in landscape with much smoother surface and many errors. I did not correct these errors because it is nearly impossible to do it automatically, it would have required hours of manual improvement. This work is not worth it because the merged dataset is very generalized and full of self-intersecting contour lines, the result still would not have been satisfying. Fortunately no survey will take part in this region so for now it can be ignored.

⁴ Often called “World File”; Can also be created manually if reference information is at hand.

Fig. 9: Erroneous contour dataset containing wrong elevation information of some single contour line parts. A hillshade of the DEM interpolated from this erroneous dataset shows dramatic cuts in landscape.

Fig. 10: The hillshade of the final DEM reveals clearly that the based dataset is a combination of different contour datasets with significant differences in quality.

5 Final Words

As already mentioned in section 3 there exists no thumb rule to always obtain a perfect hillshade because it depends of different factors. Some persons say that choosing a light source azimuth of 315° is at least one “rule” you have to follow, but what if you only want to shade a mountain ridge which has an extent exactly from north-west to south-east? In this case an azimuth of 315° might not depict the landform satisfyingly. You start to reject standards which results in trying around different settings to achieve what you imagine. I learned very much about hillshading as one crucial part of (digital) cartography and can only recommend visiting <http://www.shadedrelief.com> and <http://www.reliefshading.com> to find detailed background information on this topic.

To interpolate the raster-based DEM took the most time because at least the first tested approach (see section 2.1) delivered results slowly due to long running times of the algorithm. The results with ArcGIS (section 2.3) were most satisfying but needed much tweaking to process the whole dataset. In this context I had the chance to step deeper into Python scripting language [9] which offers the possibility to perform concatenated ArcGIS-operations to speed up the whole work process.

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